

Some Properties of Cut Locus of a Flat Torus

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Abstract : In this article, we would like to show that there is no cut point of any point in a plane, but there exists the cut locus of a point in a flat torus. By the results, we would like to determine the structure of cut locus of a flat torus.

Keywords : cut locus, flat torus, geodesics

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